

Quantifying Uncertainty in a Continuously Distributed Unresolved Resonance Range

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ABSTRACT

For decades, probability tables have been used to model the behavior of the total cross-section in the unresolved resonance range. Recently, a new formalism was proposed using a normal inverse Gaussian distribution, which both allows for continuous distribution of the cross-section and significantly reduces the memory requirement. In this work, we explore the implications of this formalism on uncertainty quantification, looking specifically at the impact on k_{eff} for the Big Ten criticality benchmark using Total Monte Carlo. Covariances were generated with a uniform uncertainty in the expected value of the total cross-section in the URRs of ^{235}U and ^{238}U assigned entirely to a single parameter of the distribution. Datasets sampled from these covariances were used as the inputs to a fast-TMC calculation, revealing that the choice of how to distribute uncertainty among the parameters of the total cross-section distribution significantly impacts both the shape of the k_{eff} distribution and the presence and magnitude of outliers. With this in mind, we recommend applying uncertainty only to the parameter μ , which simply shifts the mean of the distribution.

Keywords: Unresolved resonance range, Uncertainty quantification, Total Monte Carlo

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1. Unresolved Resonances

Accurate treatment of the resonance self-shielding behavior of large nuclides is highly significant to nuclear criticality and safety calculations. Unfortunately, at high energies (approximated 2 keV in ^{235}U and 20 keV in ^{238}U) spacing of the resonances becomes so small relative to their width that they can no longer be resolved experimentally. In this “unresolved resonance range” (URR), it is not always sufficient to use the mean value of the cross-section, with errors on the order of hundreds of pcm in k_{eff} for intermediate-spectrum problems [1]. In Monte Carlo calculations, it is therefore convenient to represent the URR stochastically in order to preserve the self-shielding effect.

In this paper, we examine the novel methodology for this stochastic treatment proposed recently by Ridley, et al. in the context of uncertainty quantification [2]. We explore the impact of assigning the uncertainty in the total cross-section in the URR to each of the parameters of this novel continuous distribution and propose best practices for generating covariance in this formalism.

1.2. Probability Tables

The traditional method for this stochastic treatment of the URR is to use probability tables. Originally proposed by Levitt in 1972, probability tables are generated by sampling random sets of possible resonances from known statistical laws [3]. The probability that the cross-section in a given energy range falls between certain bounds is then tabulated into a histogram that can be stored and sampled during a Monte Carlo calculation when a particle scatters into that energy range. This approach allows the impact of self-shielding in the URR to be accounted for, without the significant computational cost required to generate pointwise cross-sections on-the-fly.

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1.3. Continuous URR Representation

This table lookup method, however, is not well-suited for use on GPUs, which recently led Ridley to develop a continuous representation of the URR as part of his doctoral thesis [4, 5]. The total cross-section at a given energy was distributed according to a normal inverse Gaussian distribution, rather than a histogram, reducing the memory cost to only four variables at each energy and temperature. The conditional partial cross-sections are also fitted to a continuous function using barycentric rational polynomials, though the focus of this work will be on the total cross-section distribution¹.

1.4. Normal Inverse Gaussian Distribution

The normal inverse Gaussian (NIG) distribution is a particularly good candidate for modeling the total cross-section distribution, because it is capable of matching a number of observed behaviors [2]:

- For widely spaced resonances, the cross-section distribution approaches a Cauchy.
- For very densely spaced resonances, the cross-section distribution approaches a Gaussian.
- At intermediate values, the cross-section distribution has linear asymptotes when plotted in log-probability.

The probability density function of the NIG distribution is deceptively complex:

$$f(x; \alpha, \beta, \mu, \delta) = \frac{\alpha \delta K_1 \left(\alpha \sqrt{\delta^2 + (x - \mu)^2} \right)}{\pi \sqrt{\delta^2 + (x - \mu)^2}} e^{\delta \gamma + \beta(x - \mu)} \quad (1)$$

where $\gamma \equiv \sqrt{\alpha^2 - \beta^2}$ and K_1 is the first-order modified Bessel function of the second kind. Sampling from a NIG distribution, however, is relatively easy:

$$\begin{aligned} \sigma_t &\sim \mathcal{N}(\mu + \beta z, z) \\ z &\sim \text{IG}(\delta, \gamma) \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

The mean of a NIG distribution also has a very simple form:

$$E[\sigma_t] = \mu + \frac{\delta \beta}{\gamma} \quad (3)$$

Though the NIG distribution is most often parametrized as $f(x; \alpha, \beta, \mu, \delta)$, as shown above, there are a number of benefits to instead using the form $f(x; \gamma, \beta, \mu, \delta)$, where $\alpha \equiv \sqrt{\gamma^2 + \beta^2}$. Most intuitively, these are the parameters that show up in the mean and in sampling. Additionally, the standard parametrization has the constraint that $\alpha > \beta$ (and Ridley showed that $\beta > 0$ is a good assumption for this specific application). This complicates the process of sampling valid perturbations of the distribution for uncertainty quantification. By contrast, parametrizing in terms of γ requires only that $\gamma, \beta > 0$, which is much simpler to implement. Finally, γ can be considered a proxy for the resonance density, at least asymptotically: for $\gamma \rightarrow 0$, the distribution approaches a Cauchy, and for $\gamma \rightarrow \infty$, it approaches a Gaussian (with $\beta = 0$ in both cases).

2. METHODS

2.1. Covariance Generation

Parameter covariances were generated to match a target uncertainty in the pointwise cross-section at each energy and temperature. For the purposes of this work, a uniform 10% uncertainty (3σ) was used

¹The expected values of the capture and fission partial cross-sections, given a sampled total cross-section, are calculated as described, then subtracted from that total cross-section to obtain the elastic scattering partial cross-section.

for ^{235}U and 5% for ^{238}U . This is larger than the actual experimental uncertainty, in order to better resolve integral effects, but within the right order of magnitude [6]. Additionally, two simplifying assumptions were made about the correlation matrix:

- At a given energy, the uncertainty in the cross-section at all temperatures is perfectly correlated. This is well justified, following from the fact that although they cannot be experimentally measured, the resonances in the URR *do* exist and will be the same at all temperatures, even though the distributions were fit independently.
- The uncertainty in the cross-section at all energies in the URR will be treated as perfectly correlated. This is a strictly inaccurate, but not unfounded, simplification. Experimental data, plotted in Figure 1, shows that the URR is in fact highly correlated for both ^{235}U and ^{238}U [6].

Figure 1. Experimental uncertainty in the URR is highly correlated for both (a) ^{235}U and (b) ^{238}U .

Because each energy and temperature has its own independent NIG distribution, matching the desired uncertainty in the mean cross-section becomes simply a matter of finding the correct uncertainty in the parameter under investigation. This was done iteratively by arbitrarily choosing an initial relative standard deviation and updating it based on the measured uncertainty in the mean. Taking μ as an example:

$$\sigma_{n+1}^{\mu(E,T)} = \sigma_n^{\mu(E,T)} \times \left(\frac{\sigma_{target}^{E[\sigma_t(E,T)]}}{\sigma_n^{E[\sigma_t(E,T)]}} \right) \quad (4)$$

This was iterated simultaneously for every energy and temperature in a nuclide, until all values were within 10% (relative) of the target uncertainty². Once again using μ as an example, this time specifically for ^{235}U , this is shown in Figure 2.

2.2. Big Ten Criticality Benchmark

“Big Ten” was a critical assembly built at Los Alamos National Laboratory and extensively documented for benchmarking purposes in the 1970s [7]. It consists of 10% enriched uranium metal surrounded

²If, for example, the target is 5% uncertainty, the acceptable range is 4.5–5.5% uncertainty.

Figure 2. The uncertainty in the mean total cross-section at every energy and temperature in the URR of ^{235}U matches closely with the target values of 10%. The energy points used were inherited from the ENDF resonance data

by alternating plates of natural and highly enriched (93%) uranium, with a depleted uranium (0.2%) reflector.

Big Ten is included in the International Handbook of Evaluated Criticality Safety Benchmark Experiments and has been shown to be sensitive to changes in the treatment of the URR [8, 1]. The OpenMC model of Big Ten used in this work was created by Paul Romano in 2012, based on Mosteller et al's expanded criticality validation suite for MCNP [9].

2.3. Total Monte Carlo

The total Monte Carlo (TMC) method for uncertainty quantification was originally proposed in 2008 by Koning and Rochman [10]. In general, this consists of generating a large number of perturbed nuclear data libraries and using each as the input to an identical independent Monte Carlo simulation. The total variance in any tally calculated by these simulations, such as k_{eff} , can then be decomposed as:

$$\sigma_{observed}^2 = \overline{\sigma_{stat}^2} + \sigma_{ND}^2 \quad (5)$$

where $\overline{\sigma_{stat}^2}$ is the average statistical variance of the Monte Carlo simulations and σ_{ND}^2 is the variance due to nuclear data uncertainty. One of the main benefits of TMC over more traditional linear sensitivity methods is that it can expose non-linear effects. In linear sensitivity methods, the relationship between inputs and outputs is assumed to be, as the name suggests, linear; if the inputs vary according to a Gaussian distribution, as here, the outputs are assumed to as well [11]. TMC calculations performed in OpenMC using a benchmark model of Big Ten and continuous URR datasets sampled from the covariance matrices generated in Section 2.1 can expose not only whether the choice of which NIG parameters to assign uncertainty to impacts the scalar uncertainty in k_{eff} , but also whether the *shape* of the k_{eff} distribution differs from the Gaussian that would be imposed by a linear sensitivity analysis.

2.3.1. Fast TMC

More specifically, the technique used in this work is so-called "fast TMC," outlined in another paper by Rochman et al. in 2014 [12]. The key difference from the original TMC is that each Monte Carlo

simulation is initialized with a different seed. This allows significantly fewer neutron histories to be run in each simulation: the original TMC methodology required that the statistical uncertainty be converged well below the nuclear data uncertainty ($\overline{\sigma_{stat}} \approx 0.05 \times \sigma_{observed}$). With fast TMC, this requirement decreases to $\overline{\sigma_{stat}} \approx 0.5 \times \sigma_{observed}$.

3. RESULTS

3.1. Criticality Results

For each case (γ , β , μ , and δ), 250 datasets were sampled. For each, criticality calculations on Big Ten were run in OpenMC, using 1000 inactive batches, 10000 active batches, and 10000 particles per batch [13]. The histograms for each are plotted in Figure 3. Clearly, the choice of parameter significantly impacts the shape of the distribution of k_{eff} : While the μ results appear Gaussian, the β results are skewed slightly to the right, and the results for δ and γ exhibit positive and negative kurtosis, respectively.

Figure 3. The distributions of k_{eff} for (a) γ , (b) β , (c) μ , and (d) δ differ in shape, but have approximately the same bounds, excepting extreme outliers which were not plotted.

These plots, however, obscure the most significant difference between the distributions: the presence and magnitude of outliers. The γ case had an outlier of 1.0055, β of 1.0045, and δ of 1.0031, compared to the vast majority of samples, which fell within 1.0034 – 1.0040. This has significantly more impact on the

observed nuclear data uncertainty (and its variance), tabulated in Table I, than the shape of the rest of the distribution. The variance of the nuclear data uncertainty was estimated using the jackknife method [14]. The variance of the statistical uncertainty was found using the same method to be negligible.

Table I. Criticality results for Big Ten

NIG Parameter	γ	β	μ	δ
Statistical Uncertainty	6.8 pcm	6.8 pcm	6.8 pcm	6.8 pcm
Nuclear Data Uncertainty	13.2 ± 6.0 pcm	8.7 ± 1.7 pcm	8.3 ± 0.7 pcm	9.4 ± 1.0 pcm
ND Unc. (Excluding Outliers)	5.9 ± 0.5 pcm	7.2 ± 0.7 pcm	8.3 ± 0.7 pcm	8.6 ± 0.7 pcm
Impact of Outliers	+7.3 pcm	+1.5 pcm	0.0 pcm	+1.1 pcm

3.2. Cross-section Perturbation Analysis

The basis for meaningful comparison between the parameters was that the variance in the mean total cross-section would be the same across all cases (uniformly 10% in ^{235}U and 5% in ^{238}U). It is therefore unsurprising that the nuclear data uncertainty, excluding outliers, is comparable.

The mean of the total cross-section distribution, however, is not the only value that impacts k_{eff} . After all, the whole point of probabilistic modeling of the URR is that simply using the mean value (equivalent to setting all the higher moments to zero), is insufficient [1]. Though it is possible that analysis of the very high-order behavior of the distribution could yield insight into the shape differences observed in Figure 3, the outlier behavior can be well explained simply by looking at how each parameter impacts the variance.

The variance of the total cross-section distribution is given by:

$$\text{Var}[\sigma_t] = \frac{\delta a^2}{\gamma^3} = \frac{\delta (\gamma^2 + \beta^2)}{\gamma^3} \quad (6)$$

The first thing to note is that μ does not contribute to the variance (or any higher moments, for that matter), which explains why the corresponding distribution is simply Gaussian. The variance changes linearly with δ , quadratically with β , and according to a more complicated trend with γ , which converges asymptotically to $1/\gamma$ but, for small values, is significantly larger and more sensitive to perturbations. All this means that the variance in the total cross-section is most sensitive to γ , then to β , and least sensitive to δ . This corresponds exactly with the observed behavior of outliers. By far the most extreme outlier was observed when perturbing γ , then β , then δ , with no outliers samples when perturbing μ , which does not impact the variance.

4. CONCLUSIONS

Representing the total cross-section in the unresolved resonance range using a normal inverse Gaussian distribution is a powerful technique for reducing the memory requirement of nuclear data in this range, but care must be taken when applying it to uncertainty quantification. The impact of many of the parameters on integral reactor physics metrics like k_{eff} is non-linear and can be unpredictable. Though the uncertainty in k_{eff} was mostly dependent on the uncertainty in the expected value of the total cross-section, the impact of nonlinearity and outliers from perturbing γ , β , and δ cannot be disregarded.

The simplest and safest way to propagate uncertainty in the URR using this method would be to apply all uncertainty to μ , which was observed to result in a well-behaved Gaussian distribution, without significant outliers. Though this is perfectly fine for representing long-range systemic uncertainty, we

recognize that it is not guaranteed to accurately capture the impact of uncertainty in the resonance parameters of the URR. If it is desirable to, for instance, explicitly apply uncertainty in the resonance spacing to γ , this should be done only with the recognition that the resulting distribution is unlikely to be Gaussian and therefore may be difficult to characterize. In general, however, we would caution against applying uncertainty to parameters other than μ , in lieu of data suggesting specific non-Gaussian behavior.

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